

Socioeconomics for the 21st Century

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Abstract

A review-based neuroeconomic model of decision-making (NeM) identifies general risk-willingness as a parameter of economic behavior with crucial implications to more domains of Socioeconomics:

1. NeM orders the Big5 personalities into a simplified model for sensitivity training of managers. NeM elaborates on the Pilot-in-the-plane model of entrepreneurship, too.

2. Neuroeconomic trials show man is neither egoist or altruist but a hybrid with a cultural potential for development of democracy beyond classical fighting of wings towards collaboration across-the-center on issues of common interest (strong economic-political reciprocity). Such strong reciprocity is required towards global threats such as 1) CO2 Tariff towards global warming and 2) Universal Basic Income (UBI) for redistribution. A primary target group for promotion of such strong reciprocity is found in social liberal political movements as confirmed by a Field Study of Danish social liberals.

3. NeM explains too meditative in-depth-relaxation as effective towards epidemic job-related stress.

Discussion focuses on responses to this approach to Socioeconomics from other social scientists.

Keywords: Neuroeconomics, Big5, Political Economy, stress-management, UBI, Simple Living.

Introduction

In a classical local market, economic growth is driven by the profit incentive evoking entrepreneurial ingenuity to develop new, better and cheaper products for consumers. What it takes of consumers is only a general ability to choose the buying alternative providing the best value-for-money. History has proven that this ability, despite short-comings, is so consolidated in the population that market-based growth has raised the average buying power of money many fold compared to the pre-industrial level in the Century Feudal village society. Further this model of growth is self-stabilizing (E) as high profits in an early stage of the development of a new line of products are supposed to be normalized by competition among entrepreneurs. Monopolized markets were special cases regulated by Anti-monopolist legislation, for instance regarding the supply of energy. The market-based vision of growth has passed more phases since Smith 1789. The First Phase from about 1750 focused on mechanics such as the "Spinning Jenny" and steam engines. The Second Phase from about 1870 was based on electricity and later combustion engines. Inventions that enabled mass production, for instance of cars.

Since 1970, a Third Phase of Digitizing has developed adding complexity to scaling. The globalization of digital technology is now so dominant that the basic laws of market economy have turned upside-down as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. From Local to Global Markets

In such a globalized market economy, production costs are no longer declining at the large scale. The comparative advantages for multinational companies (MNC) minimizes unit costs, see profit formula (termed Revenue-of-Investment (ROI)) below [Larsen, 2021a]:

$$ROI = Qx(M - 1)Vc - F(Y, i) \quad ROI = Qx(M-1)Vx - F[Y,i]$$

Q_x = quantity produced per period; M = profit margin on variable unit costs (V_c).

However, the consumer price must cover the fixed costs (F) to production equipment, too:

F is often a function of the expected life-time of equipment (Y) and the borrowing rate (i).

(1) Ownership encompasses the development of proprietary technology. MNC are often technological leaders that invest heavily in developing new products, processes and brands, which are kept confidential and protected by intellectual property rights. Investment costs per sold unit ($F(Y,i)$) decline proportionately with scale (Q_x).

(2) Relocalization benefits include that the headquarters and/or special departments near the final buyers or closer to cheaper labor, expert engineering, raw materials and tax shelter. A crucial path to reduce variable unit costs (V_c).

(3) Internalization of benefits from owning a technology, brand, expertise, or patent that is risky or unprofitable to rent or license to another corporation due difficulties enforcing international contracts. This makes in general public control of core factors of ROI non-transparent without very close international collaboration.

In contrast to the enormous benefits to MNC, the globalized economy overwhelms strong negative side-effects to the collective society, for instance:

- 1) “The Greenhouse effect” documented by IPCC [IPCC, 2021]
- 2) Rising economic inequality as documented for instance by IMF and [Piketty, 2014]
- 3) Epidemic job-related stress as documented by WHO [Markus et al, 2012]

These market failures require new specific policy interventions. Socioeconomics must cover both individual and social aspects. A prototype of such restructure of Economics is modern healthcare that applies a 2-stage methodology for development of new pharmaceuticals. Firstly, the action-mechanism of potential new interventions are investigated in a laboratory setting. Secondly, the laboratory findings are user-tested for finalization.

Method

This neuroeconomic approach to Socioeconomics must consider all of Neurology, Economics and Psychology, wherefore international science databases such as EconLit, PubMed and PsychInfo are searched for relevant studies:

1. The “Laboratory” setting for socioeconomic behavior is the Triune Conception of Brain and Behavior concluding our brain mirrors biological evolution, see Figure 2 [McLean, 2002]. The BrainStem is the Reptile level ruled by the survival instinct. The middle brain (Limbic Brain) is the Mammal level that's fully integrated with the Reptile level in man. On top of the Limbic Brain, Neocortex contains higher-order thinking centering integration in the Frontal Brain. In All, basal neurodynamics is between Frontal Cognition (Y-axis) and Limbic motivation which is an ambivalent function of reward-seeking and risk-aversion determining the degree of “Autonomic Arousal” (ANS as X-axis).

Figure 2. The Triune Conception of Brain and Behavior

2. To finalize laboratory findings for practical use the 5 criteria on field studies in behavioral economics must be fulfilled [List, 2021]:

1 Evidence Base

Studies referenced as evidence must be rooted in positivist science, for instance:

- Primary population data, see [Florida, 2012]
- Sample Tests, see [Saraswathy et al., 2001]
- Randomized trials, see [Maclean, 1997]
- Qualitative Investigations, see [Dohmen et al., 2005]
- Reviews of randomized trials including meta-analysis, see [Manzoni et al., 2008]
- Cross Correlations between randomized trials, see [Becker et al., 2012]

2 Representativeness to a Population

Classical domains of Economics: Consumer Behavior, Production and Political Economy

3 Representativeness to the Situation

Global threats identified in the Introduction must be faced

4 Spillovers

The laboratory findings open new application options, for instance gender economics

5 Economies of Scale

The utility is huge in disseminating economic knowledge (Human Capital) [Becker, 1993].

Results

1 Neuroeconomic Model (NeM)

The mainstream state of relation between the 2 basal neurodynamic processes derived from Figure 2 is the dual process theory (DPT) by Nobel Laureate Kahneman [2011]. The essence of DPT is that ANS (Type 1 System) is fast, reactive, automatic, intuitive, heuristic, associative, and unconscious (or preconscious) and associated with perceptual and affective operations like attentional cueing and motor-response preparation. On top, Frontal Cognition (Type 2 System) is in contrast slow, controlled, reflective, serial, rule-based, effortful, and conscious, and associated with intensive cognitive tasks like deductive reasoning.

Neuroeconomics has elaborated the understanding of Type 1-2 Systems by trials on decision-making. A meta-analysis specifies the Frontal correlates to the Type 1 System as an Orbito Frontal - Ventromedial axis producing “Expected Utility” [Levy&Glimcher, 2012]. The correlates to the Type 2 System are specified as an Frontal Ventromedial - Dorsolateral axis recollecting our memories for comparison with our expectations [Hare et al., 2014]. Finally, the Frontopolar - Ventromedial axis is identified as the center of integration of expectations (Type 1 System) and memories (Type 2 System) [Koechlin&Hyafil, 2007].

A series of neuroeconomic trials specify the integration of Type 1-2 Systems:

A line of trials focus on Intertemporal choices (IC) [McClure et al., 2006] asking participants about their preference for either an instant payment of 1000 USD or 1500 USD in a year. A minority prefer the smaller instant payment, because the delay of one year is too complex a decision. Simultaneous scanner records show a majority of rational decision-makers accepting a delayed payment peaking Frontal Cognition at a

moderate ANS. A minority of risk-averse decision-makers are dominated by ANS at a low Frontal Cognition.

Another line of trials on explorative choices (EC) [Daw et al., 2005] asks participants about their preference for a fixed reward or the chance to get a far larger reward with a such low probability that the long-term outcome is lower than the fixed reward. Participants taking the chance for a higher reward have a scanner-profile with low risk-aversion at a moderate cognitive activity which gives more space to imaginative (associative) impulses from the Visuo-spatial center in the Intraparietal Cortex.

These trials determine the shape of the functional relationship between Frontal Cognition and ANS as curvilinear, see Figure 3 [Larsen, 2021b]. So, general Risk-willingness - the ability to overcome risk-aversion - is identified as a broad parameter of economic behavior. Risk-willingness correlates strongly with important behavioral domains: 1) Career ($r=0.61$), 2) Financial Matter ($r=0.56$), 3) Sports ($r=0.5$), 4) Health ($r=0.48$) and 5) Driving ($r=0.49$) [Dohmen et al., 2005]. So, Risk-willingness must replace the Neoclassical Paradigm of Bounded Rationality (BR) [Simon, 1955] and other social dogmas as the general parameter of economic behavior.

Figure 3. Neuroeconomic Model (NeM)

The practical application of NeM and related findings is analyzed in the sections below:

- Section 2 Business Psychology
- Section 3 Post Industrial Consumer Behavior
- Section 4 Political Economy

2 Business Psychology

2.1 Psychological Sensitivity

5 basal personality traits are identified by correlations between empirical studies of personality [Goldberg, 1993]. The Big5 adds a new Temper to the 4 classical Tempers, the Open-minded. The genetic rooting of extreme Tempers as Extraversion and Neuroticism makes them rather inflexible. Open-mindedness is an in-between Temper that grows from Conscientiousness by Liberal upbringing, tertiary education and personal life experiences in family and business life. Big5 relates to an index of economic preferences (Dohmen Scale 0-10) [Becker et al., 2012] as summarized in Table 1 where Extravert and Open-minded correlate positively with the Dohmen Score while Conscientious, Agreeable and Neurotic correlate negatively. The broad validity of the Big5 is for instance demonstrated in a Doctoral Dissertation prognosticating students' choice among Majors [Vedel, 2016]. Neuroeconomic Psychology changes the behavioral focus from individuals to group processes where Open-minded plays a key role both regarding internal communication in R&D Groups [Kern, 2019] and formation of consumer norms [Gountas and Corciari, 2010].

Table 1. Neuroeconomic Psychology

Positive Correlation with Risk-will

Extravert

Open-minded

Negative Correlation with Risk-will

Conscientious

Agreeable

(Neurotic)

- Stimulated by Other	-Receptive to Argument	- Organized	- Collaborative	- Easy negative
- Outbouded	- Cultural experience/Aesthetics	- Responsible	- Considerate	- Easy Angry
- Energetic	- Curious / Innovative	- Diligent	- Orderly /Quiet	- Easy
- Talkative	- Not consistent/cautious	- Efficiency-oriented	- Sympathetic	Anxious
- No Reservations		- No Procrastinations	- Non-selfish	- Vulnerable
				- Worried
Sanguine	?	Phlegmatic	Melancholic	Choleric

Source: Based on Becker et al. 2012: Relations btw. Economic Preferences and Psychological Personality

Table 2 shows the core for training of psychological sensitivity. Ask yourself / others which type you resemble the most to develop your sensitivity by trial and error (The diagnosis Neuroticism is omitted for use among laymen):

Table 2. Heuristic for Sensitivity Training

- Stimulated by Other	-Receptive to Argument	- Organized	- Collaborative
- Outbouded	- Culture/Aesthetic experience	- Responsible	- Considerate
- Energetic	- Curious / Innovative	- Diligent	- Orderly /Quiet
- Talkative	- Not consistent/cautious	- Efficiency-oriented	- Sympathetic
- No Reservations		- No Procrastinations	- Non-selfish
☐	☐	☐	☐

2.2 Pilot-in-the-plane entrepreneurship as prototype for the creative class

NeM explains how creative thinking differs from goal-directedness (Peak Cognition). Creative thinking happens at a moderate analytic intensity driven by positivity rather than negativity, see Figure 3. Figure 4 illustrates the profile of a creative man, operated as Pilot-in-the-plane Entrepreneur with the following traits [Saraswathy et al., 2001]:

- **Crazy Quilt:** The entrepreneur is *Open-minded* with a good ability to communicate and collaborate with others. An crucial quality to build a versatile team
 - **Affordable loss:** An entrepreneur is not ruled by mono-disciplinary profit maximization as supposed by classical economics. His focus on economy is moderated to an alternative Worst-case budget defining an eventual necessity to stop of project
 - **Bird-in-hand:** An entrepreneur is not an idealist ruled by wishful thinking. He is a pragmatic sticking to tangible realities as expressed in the cited saying
 - **Lemonade:** The entrepreneur possesses a lot of optimism to overcome non-predicted difficulties as symbolized in the saying on turning sour citrus in to a sweet lemonade
- Pilot-in-the-plane Entrepreneur**

Pilot-in-the-plane is now known as the 4 principles of effectuation, because a controlled study confirms the comparative efficacy of entrepreneurs compared with other Academic educated business managers [Laurie-Martinez et al., 2005]. Pilot-in-the-plane entrepreneurship resembles classical hierarchical military management in the focus on basal discipline. However, it differs radically in the focus of promoting

individual creativity of all staff members as a sharp contrast to military execution of hierarchical instructions. In a wider societal perspective digitizing includes the rise of social media facilitating Open-mindedness and entrepreneurship to fold out creativity as claimed in the theory on “The rise of The Creative Class” [Florida, 1012]. Table 3 shows the creative class, based on recalculated data [Dohmen et al. 2005 and Andersen & Lorentzen 2005]. Since 1970, people in creative jobs valuing Open-mindedness have tripled, confirming the Florida Thesis. This is a splendid positive side-effect of globalization deserving strong attention.

Table 3. Demographic Distribution of Economic Agents (%)

Group (Score)	Neurotic (0-1)	Agreeable (2-3)	Conscientious (4-5)	Open-minded (6-7)	Extravert (8-10)
Males	2	8	16	16	8
Females	10	13	18	7	2
German SOEP 2004 (Creative Class 2023)	12	21	34 (17)	23 (40)	10

Source: Recalculated data from Dohmen et al. and Andersen & Lorentzen 2005.

The creative class divides into a super-creative core that includes those that constitute ‘directly creative activity’, creative professionals, and others with a significant creative component. Members of the super-creative core are classified by the BLS (Bureau of Labor Statistics) as working in ‘Computer and mathematical occupations’, ‘Architecture and engineering occupations’, ‘Life, physical, and social science occupations’, ‘Education, training, and library occupations’, and ‘Arts, design, entertainment, sports, and media occupations’. Florida maintains that there are others who, at least to some extent, involve the creation of meaningful new forms (e.g. shopkeepers, chefs, creatively oriented factory workers) that too should thus be thought of as part of the creative class. The 3T (Talent, Tolerance and Technology) characterize the essence of the creative class.

The Florida thesis is criticized by both economists and other social scientists as superficial, lacking evidence on more substantial changes in modern urban life [Peck, 2005]. However, it's strongly supported by both our data in Table 3 as well as a European research project that estimates the share of the creative class in Denmark to be +40% of the workforce and still rising [Andersen & Lorentzen, 2005]. The former working-class majority, primarily complying to hierarchical instructions, is reduced to about 20% of the workforce. The new majority workforce is best characterized as creative due to job-conditions resembling classical artists that must perform independently.

2.3 Gender Economics

Feminist Economics is a relative new field emerging in the 80s as an complementary approach to welfare economics. NeM contributes to the field with clarification of gender differences in brain function. The single far most important factor differentiating ‘General risk willingness’ is gender [Dohmen et al., 2005]. Females are moderately more risk-averse in economic behavior than males (Averages: Male=5 and Female=4). The wiring of the brain explains the gender differences in the way that males have strong Frontal-Posterior connections which promote stringent deliberate thinking while females have better interhemispheric connections promoting collaboration and imagination.

A Hong Kong study examined gender differences in the distribution of creative abilities through the lens of the greater male variability hypothesis postulating that men show greater inter-individual variability than women in both physical and psychological attributes [He & Wong, 2021].

Recognizing these differences, it appears biased to develop a normative feminist economics claiming complete equalization of females to males in all socio-economic contexts. A more useful approach is to

develop a gender economics based on the complementarity of the genders synthesizing similarities as well as differences. However, regarding similarities both genders must agree on equal salary for equal jobs and equal social rights in general.

2.4 Stress-management

WHO warns about an epidemic stress load [Markus et al., 2012]. The primary neurological advice for better mental health is self-control or *stamina* based on physical fitness [Oaten & Cheng, 2006]. However, job-related stress is a growing threat that deserves special attention in modern business life! In 2020, Depression was the second leading cause of world disability. 2030 Depression is expected to be the largest burden of disease.

NeM guides stress-management as illustrated in Figure 5 where meditation affects a deep relaxation movement from the Temper circle towards Origo. Such release of preconscious blockings reveals a fourth neurodynamic factor complementing basal award-seeking, fear responses and cognition in Figure 3. Modern mantra-meditation is practiced in a relaxed sitting position for instance on a simple chair in a quiet place where thoughts are dissolved by a mantra. Such homeostatic in-dept-relaxation shows subjectively slow breathing and objectively low galvanic skin conductance [Wallace, 1970]. Analogue results are reproduced in subsequent studies, for instance at Harvard [Benson & Klipper, 1975].

Figure 5. Meditative In-depth-relaxation

Long-term effects of regular mantra meditation are demonstrated, too:

- A significant decline in the stress hormone (plasma cortisol) characterizing a more relaxed pattern of behavior [McLean, 1997]
- A meta-analysis finds that regular relaxation exercises complement physical fitness as health activity dissolves stress and anxiety [Manzoni et al., 2008]
- A 14-year, pre- and post intervention study retrospectively assessed government payments to physicians for treating the TM and comparison groups. TM reduced payments to physicians between 5 % and 13 % annually relative to comparison subjects over 6 years. Randomized study is recommended [Herron & Hillis, 2000]
- In plain language meditation is summarized as “Psychology of Silence” [Holen, 1976] A neuroeconomic guideline for restructure of cognition from the level of Origo is reinforcement of the Working Memory (WM) [Baddeley, 2010]. Key training tools are:
 - Dialogue with yourself by open questions on the interpretation of your experiences
 - Expand your vocabulary with diversified studies and communication
 - Become sufficiently competent in mathematics to develop functional models
 - Develop your practical competence rehearsing again and again Scenarios where ambitions become better and better linked to situations, issues and persons

2.5 Conclusion on Business Psychology

NeM simplifies the identification of differences in personality (Big5). Further, NeM clarifies personality differences between genders in the direction of complementarity. Finally, Open- mindedness is elaborated in the prototype of modern entrepreneurship. This Pilot-in-the- plane model by Saraswathy represents a productive alternative to the military model of Top-down management. However, business relations differ from classical humanistic values, too, in the way that they are based on mutual rather than one-sided

interests. Also, NeM guides an active healthy lifestyle offering better stress-management by pragmatic use of classical meditation techniques as a complement to physical fitness.

3 Postindustrial Consumer Behavior

A variety of Artistic activities has been a notable part of European culture since the Renaissance as continued by modern humanistic psychology [Maslow, 1962]. Maslow explains Self-actualization as the Top satisfaction of human needs. A contemporary operation of self-actualization is “Simple Living” as an alternative to “Consumerism” [Luhr, 1997]. Today, the middle class disposes of more than double of what is needed to satisfy basal physiological and social needs. Modern consumers have a basal choice between “Consumerism” and “Simple Living” as illustrated in Figure 7. Health, ecology, charity and household economy drive “Simple Living” stronger and stronger as new technical progress materializes only by lower and lower marginal consumer benefits.

Individualization expresses itself in various ways as an alternative to Consumerism:

1. The simple classical alternative to short-term consumption is savings, eventually with active investments.
A majority of modern households do savings
2. Unfoldment of neglected individual interests/talents
See also 2.2
3. Engagement in the “Common Good”-
activities, for instance Charity
Charity corresponds today to 10% of GDP whereof 2/3 private volunteers. The rest is financial donations by Funds
4. A fast growing special variant of 3 aims to reduce CO2-emission and waste of materials.
5. “Slow Living” eventually inspired by 2.

Figure 6. The Basal Consumer Choice

4 Political Economy

4.1 CO2 Tariff for “Greening” of the economy

Governments face today global warming as a common threat that must expand the political focus from nations to global interdependence, see Figure 8 [IPCC, 2021]. The most effective intervention is as clear as the threat: A Tariff on CO2-emission (ET) as claimed by Nobel Laureates Pigou 1920 and Nordhaus 2015. A broad ET and bottom-up activism across sectors are crucial, but not enough to implement a carbon neutral economy:

- Critical sectors need subsidies because they lack good energy alternatives, for instance transport by sea/air and agriculture counting for 25% of CO2 Emission
- National security plans are recommended for a rise of temperature beyond the aimed 1.5⁰ by the Paris Agreement 2015
- National policies must be closely coordinated with municipal environmental policies
- National Climate Council to guide on technology and related economics

Figure 8. The Reinforcing Greenhouse Effect

The Paris Agreement presupposes international economic solidarity as confirmed 2022 by the “Rich Global North” to the “Poor Global South” at COP27. The rich countries with large CO₂ emission should subsidize poor countries 100 billion USD per year. Supposing the rich countries are defined as G20, the subsidy amounts to 0.15% of their GDP. To the receiving poor part of the world, it represents about 0.7% of their GDP.

A major challenge to such international solidarity is that China, as the largest emitter of CO₂, must contribute to this Fund, too. So far China has been ranked as a developing economy in international treaties, for instance WTO.

4.2 Universal Basic Income (UBI)

Economic policy has an option to increase the total social welfare by redistribution policies since Stuart Mill advanced Utilitarianism 1863. Redistribution policies presupposes an overview of the effect of taxes and subsidies. A series of Nobel Laureates (Milton, Meade, Samuelson, Simon, Solow, Tinbergen and Tobin) recommend a negative income tax as the best means for redistribution, for instance as an Universal Basic Income (UBI). A classical objection to UBI claims that it weakens the labor incentive and so long-term growth. However, sample studies on UBI for social clients in Finland, reject this liberalist objection showing it provides social security with stronger work motivation [Kela, 2019]. To the middle class UBI gives net benefit in the interest of both wings leaving most of the bill to high incomes. Further, UBI enables a simplification of the personal tax system to the benefit of all. Table 4 shows a calculation example on UBI based on Danish conditions.

Table 4. Calculation Scheme for UBI

I UBI should approach 50% of median income as Poverty limit

II ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA: 1 Citizenship 2 Age: 18-25:50% / 26-65:100% / 66+:67%

III FINANCE (Gross Budget ~ 15% of GDP):

1 Set-off in subsidies; 2 Voluntary activation; 3 Restructure of Deductions and Corporate Taxation

IV EFFECTS:

1 Security for social clients; 2 Net Surplus for the Middle Class; 3 High-Incomes pay the most

4 Less Bureaucracy

4.3 Reciprocity and Political Economy

The classical distinction between Economics and politics is on third-party effects. Only the direct effects of an economic transaction between the involved buyer and seller are the object of analysis by classical Economics. Third-party effects, for instance pollution of the environment beyond buyer and seller by toxic material, are in the classical paradigm externalities that should be left to political decision-making [Pigou, 1920]. Socioeconomics must today internalize such third party effects to be able to guide democratic policies on sustainable interventions in accordance with the UN goals. Since the French Revolution 1789,

democracy has been characterized by strong polarization between the Left (Socialist) and Right (Neoliberalist) wings on economic-policy with a pending approximate 50-50% distribution of the wings in most democracies. This model is under growing stress by the internal fraction. National- conservative right-wing movements protest against guardianship from the well-educated. The left-wing is parted, too, because most of the classical working class now belong to the new creative class with minorities of radical left-wingers.

Doughnut Economics represents a comprehensive alternative approach [Raworth, 2017]. The Doughnut itself symbolizes the focus of orthodox mainstream economics. To deal with the threat of damaging the Ecosystem surrounding economic transactions, social adaptability must be improved from the social center of the Doughnut. Unfortunately, Raworth is not specific on what economic interventions are relevant for sustainable development wherefore Political Economy must be re-discovered by another approach.

Economic transactions are based on reciprocal relationships instead of fighting. Reciprocity means, broadly speaking, a primary tendency to respond “nice” to nice actions and “nasty” to nasty actions when interacting with others. So reciprocity is limited to the self-interest in having a good reputation and promoting yourself and your project to others. The common threats raised by globalization in 4.1-2 require a strong reciprocity implying solidarity on the finance of interventions for the common good. This is actually demonstrated in democracies where the finance of collective needs for healthcare, education and social security is provided by collective taxes. OECD Statistics show, such social welfare states account for both a lower share of GDP and a higher coverage of the population in comparison with the USA basing a large share of finance on private insurance [Larsen, 2021a]. Social welfare states are forerunners in promotion of strong reciprocity towards global warming, too. The Green Party is now part of the German Government. The full spectrum of democratic economic ideologies is illustrated in Figure 8. The right wing positions various degrees of belief in entrepreneurial freedom while the left wing positions various degrees of belief in equality by central managed economies. Wing-based, but center-oriented economic ideologies, are “Social Democrats” and “Social Liberals”.

Figure 8. Democratic Economic Ideologies

Social democrat worker-parties were formed in a number of European countries in the second half of the 19. Century as national parties within the 1. International Socialist Association of Workers. Social democrats focus on pragmatic improvements for the broad working-population within the democratic system retaining socialism as a long-term goal. By the 21st Century, they aim to increase welfare policies and public services within a hybrid of market economy and democratic policies, for instance by the Nordic model.

Social Liberalism developed from Utilitarianism by the end of the 19. Century where social liberalism emerged in more countries. Social liberals overlap with social democrats on social welfare policy. The first notable implementation of social liberal policies occurred under Liberal Party in Britain from 1906 until 1914 where the main elements included pensions for poor older adults, health, sickness and unemployment insurance.

These changes that were financed by progressive taxation. A scenario of stronger future democratic across-the-center collaboration is supported by shortcomings of the extreme economic-political ideologies:

- Poor Outcome of Central managed 1917-91 (Communism) [Maddison, 2012]
- Neoliberalist globalized economy implies, for instance global warming [IPCC, 2021]

In the USA, lacking a large Left-wing party, policies of strong reciprocity presuppose a long-term dominance of the Democratic compared to the Neoliberalist Republican Party. China is actually the largest economy of the world indicated by Purchasing Power Parities (PPP) based on consumer buying power rather than currency exchange rates. In 2019, last year before Covid-19, China produced 2850 billion PPP exceeding the US by 25%. The Chinese cultural base is Confucianism accepting natural hierarchies where authorities must be kept up to their obligations by the population. The logic of the Chinese Revolution 1947 was that the Emperor did not deliver the expected economic growth. The National People's Congress (NPC) is the legislative body of contemporary China with representatives directly elected by the people. NPC had 2980 non-salaried members in 2018 as the World's largest legislative body. NPC meets only in full session for roughly two weeks each year while most of NPC's legislative power is delegated to the Standing Committee (NPCSC) with 170 legislators and continuous bi-monthly meetings. The autocracy of the Chinese state is due to control of the free election of members to the NPC by the Chinese Communist Party (CCP).

In India, an acute balance of payments crisis in 1991 led to the adoption of a broad economic liberalization. Since the start of the 21st century, annual average GDP growth has been 6% to 7% and from 2013 to 2018, Indian growth even surpassed China. Today, It is the fifth in the world by nominal GDP and the third by PPP. Due to the relative peaceful deliberation process the economic-political spectrum is not the traditional fighting of wings. Economic-policy has now transitioned from a mixed planned economy to a mixed middle-income economy with a social-liberal economic policy. For environmental protection by a CO2 Tariff, the special Indian challenge is that GDP per capita is still so low that pressures for basal economic growth are very strong. India must, according to the World Bank 2019 Report, focus on public sector reform, infrastructure, agriculture and rural development.

4.4 Field Study on Economic-political Preferences

A development of democratic economy from the fighting of wings towards collaboration across-the-center is such a historical development that it must be tested before conclusion. The thesis from Figure 8 is that social liberal movements are a central end-user group for the practical implementation of Socioeconomics. UBI matches the original social liberal target of redistribution (4.2) and ET towards global warming (4.1) matches social liberal across-the-center collaboration for the following reasons:

- The effectiveness of ET relies in the liberal preference for entrepreneurial ingenuity
- Part of the ET-revenue can be used to social compensations in accordance with the left-wing

A field study of preferences for economic policy among members of the social liberal party in Odense Dk is summarized in Table 5. 15 members or 50% of active members (total number of formal members are higher) replied to the Questionnaire with the INFO-page in the Appendix. 27 persons with an average age of 33 years and 65% females are in the control group. The average age of controls is 42 years and the gender distribution is close to fifty-fifty in Denmark. The significance of the differences between the controls and the total population can be extrapolated from a database documenting the Dohmen Scale. The difference in age (9 years) increases the expected score 1 promille. The over-representation of females (15%) lowers the expected score 1.5%. In All, the expected score of the controls is 1.5% lower than the total population.

Table 5. Comparison of Economic-political Preferences between Social Liberals and Controls

Group	Open-minded	ET Tariff	UBI	Meditation
Social Liberals (n=15)	33%	8.7	5.3	3.5
Controls(n=27)	11%	6.1	4.4	5.9

Difference (STD) 22%* (13.5%) 2.6* (1.3) 0.9 -2.4 (1.6)

Note: * indicates statistical significance (5% Confidence level) at a one-sided test $Z \geq 1.65$.

The main finding is that fighting global warming with ET is the Top economic-political priority for both social liberals and a control group representative to the whole Danish population. However, the social liberal preference for ET is, too, statistically significantly higher than that of the controls (whole population). An explanation of the high social liberal preference for ET is the significant high share of Open-minded persons, recall Table 1 in 2.1. It was expected that social liberals had a significantly higher preference for UBI, too, but they were at the same moderate level in both groups. Meditation courses are preferred moderately more among controls which is explained by the significantly larger share of females. An additional very important learning arises from the comments of 20% of the participants. More members in both the experimental and control groups find it difficult to indicate their economic-political preferences on the basis of the short background information in the Appendix. In such cases, the preferences are typically moderated to 5. Such insecurity calls for better dissemination to the public of general socioeconomic recommendations. Such massive public information is hypothesized to have a very positive effect on the formation of public economic-political preferences in accordance with socioeconomic recommendations.

Discussion

Already 1641, Descartes recognized the dilemma of positivist science as a reductionism parting cognition in subjective and objective sub-systems. The neuroeconomic approach (NeM) solves the dilemma respecting the 5 criteria of “Field Studies in Behavioral Economics” [List, 2021]. Such an open Socioeconomic approach relates directly to other disciplines, such as Psychology (Big5) and Ecology (IPCC Climate Model). Identifying Risk- aversion as a parameter of economic behavior delivers new tools for Business Psychology, consumer behavior and democratic coalitions across-the-center (strong reciprocity) on climate protection by a CO2 Tariff and redistribution policy by UBI. The reception of such ideas by collegial social scientists was tested in Academia Letter 4873 [Larsen, 2022]:

- The reader's interest has been overwhelming! In a few months several 1.000`s visited my site on Academia Edu elevating my profile to the Top 1% of scientists, see [https://www.academia.edu/72952541/Economic Psychology](https://www.academia.edu/72952541/Economic_Psychology)
- Several hundreds of contacts are made to the visitors and surprisingly little negative criticism is received. The closest professional interest group is 100+ social scientists with an applicator interest in practical neuro-management. As a practical result Dr Jyoti Satispathy has founded the Institute for Neuro-management and Economic Studies (INMES) as a Forum for development along this line.

In All, the profile of the responders seem to indicate that the professional interest for such new Socioeconomics, primarily is among social scientists in the developing countries rather than in the developed countries.

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This project was initiated many years ago as a student learning Transcendental Meditation (TM) which made me devote my career to understanding that type of brain processes. Later on, I became aware of Neuroeconomics as a possible path forward within my formal field of Economics. Thanks to the Organisation of Transcendental Meditation!

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APPENDIX

Preferences for Economic Policy

Read the Note below, then fill-in the Query and email it to:XXX@ZZZZZ.yy.

BACKGROUND INFORMATION

1 Gender: Male (X): Female (X): Other (X): **2 Birth Date:**

3 Professional education:

4 Which of the following Personality Profiles do you resemble the most:

A Stimulates by Other; Talkative; Outgoing; Energetic

B Receptive to knowledge, aesthetics and culture;
Curious/innovative - not consistent/cautious

C Organized; Responsible; Hard working; Efficiency oriented

D Friendly; Collaborative; Emphatic; Non-selfish

PREFERENCES FOR SPECIFIC ECONOMIC POLICIES

5. Preference for Broad CO2 Tariff towards Global Warming

6. Preference for Universal Basic Income for Economic Equality

7. Preference for Meditation Course for Stress-management

Additional information: _____

Note on Socioeconomics and Sustainable Development

The UN Sustainable Goals relegate Neoclassical Economics focusing GDP. Mankind must face negative side-effects of globalization such as Global warming, Rising inequality and Epidemic stress.

A Broad CO2 Tariff towards the Global Warming documented by IPCC

Nobel Laureates from Pigou (1920) through Nordhaus (2015) recommend a CO2 Tariff (ET) towards Global Warming, because it establishes a strong and differentiated financial incentive to develop alternative carbon neutral products. ET simply activates the entrepreneurial ingenuity that has developed the damage. A counter-argument towards ET is that it is passed-over to the poorest consumers, but the incentive is largely unaffected using the revenue for social compensation.

ET must have Top priority in environmental protection, but it cannot stand- alone. Critical sectors such as transport by air/sea and agriculture lack so far the same obvious alternatives as electricity, heating and private cars. Also, the municipality levels have special opportunities to establish close collaboration with firms, institutions, associations. A national advisory climate council is crucial. ET is facilitated by democratic coalitions across-the-center as historically advanced by Social Liberals and Social Democrats from each side of the political spectrum.

Universal Basic Income (UBI) towards growing economic inequality shown by IMF

Nobel Laureates Milton, Meade, Samuelson, Simon, Solow, Tinbergen and Tobin all recommend a negative income tax (UBI) as the best means for tax-based redistribution of income. Also it simplifies the modern jungle of public subsidies and deductions. A Finnish sample study of UBI shows that it's not reducing the incentive to work. Medical research shows UBI reduces the social inequality in health. A fiscal analysis shows it can be financed by set offs and canceling of deductions.

Stress-management by Meditative In-depth-relaxation as recommended by WHO

Meditation is evidenced as a simple mental procedure to produce a state of extraordinary neurophysiological relaxation. A useful tool in a society of options with stress as the backside.

Model of Collaborative Democratic Economy

One-dimensional ideologies such as Neoliberalism and Communism are outdated by modern socioeconomic research. Now natural solidarity, as demonstrated by neuroeconomic trials, elevates democratic collaboration across-the-center towards common threats, for instance on the climate.

Model of Democratic Collaboration Across-the-center